

1 **Title:**

2 Refugia under threat: mass bleaching of coral assemblages in high-latitude eastern Australia

3

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48

49 **Abstract**

50 Environmental anomalies that trigger negative physiological responses and mortality are
51 occurring with increasing frequency due to climate change. At species' range peripheries,
52 environmental anomalies are particularly concerning because species often exist at their
53 environmental tolerance limits and may not be able to migrate to escape unfavourable
54 conditions. Here, we investigated the bleaching response and mortality of 14 coral genera
55 across high-latitude eastern Australia during a global heat stress event in 2016. We evaluated
56 whether the severity of assemblage-scale and genus-level bleaching responses was associated
57 with cumulative heat stress and/or local environmental history, including long-term mean
58 temperatures during the hottest month of each year (SST_{LTMAX}), and annual fluctuations in
59 water temperature (SST_{VAR}) and solar irradiance ($PARZ_{VAR}$). The most severely-bleached
60 genera included species that were either endemic to the region (*Pocillopora aliciae*) or rare in
61 the tropics (e.g. *Porites heronensis*). *Pocillopora* spp., in particular, showed high rates of
62 immediate mortality. Bleaching severity of *Pocillopora* was high where SST_{LTMAX} was low or
63 $PARZ_{VAR}$ was high, whereas bleaching severity of *Porites* was directly associated with
64 cumulative heat stress. While many tropical *Acropora* species are extremely vulnerable to
65 bleaching, the *Acropora* species common at high latitudes, such as *A. glauca* and *A.*
66 *solitaryensis*, showed little incidence of bleaching and immediate mortality. Two other
67 regionally-abundant genera, *Goniastrea* and *Turbinaria*, were also largely unaffected by the
68 thermal anomaly. The severity of assemblage-scale bleaching responses was poorly explained
69 by the environmental parameters we examined. Instead, the severity of assemblage-scale
70 bleaching was associated with local differences in species abundance and taxon-specific
71 bleaching responses. The marked taxonomic disparity in bleaching severity, coupled with high
72 mortality of high-latitude endemics, point to climate-driven simplification of assemblage
73 structures and progressive homogenisation of reef functions at these high-latitude locations.

74 **INTRODUCTION**

75 The distribution of global biodiversity is undergoing substantial modifications as climate
76 change accelerates and environmental anomalies become more frequent and severe (Butchart
77 et al., 2010; Cheung et al., 2009; Parmesan & Yohe, 2003; Sala et al., 2000). One such climate-
78 driven reconfiguration of global biodiversity during interglacial periods is linked to the
79 propensity for cold-adapted species to migrate further toward the poles or to contract their
80 distributions to range cores and for warm-adapted species to move toward range peripheries or
81 to pursue *ex situ* refugia. This phenomenon, also termed ‘tropicalisation’ of high-latitude
82 communities, is prevalent in both geological (Gavin et al., 2014; Greenstein & Pandolfi, 2008;
83 Stewart, Lister, Barnes, & Dalen, 2010) and contemporary records (Chen, Hill, Ohlemuller,
84 Roy, & Thomas, 2011; Parmesan & Yohe, 2003; Vergés et al., 2019; Wernberg et al., 2016),
85 highlighting the significance of high-latitude regions in the persistence of many species under
86 climate change. Interestingly, introduction of tropical species into high-latitude communities
87 is not the only driver of contemporary changes in high-latitude community compositions.
88 Climate-mediated changes in species interactions following the introduction of vagrant species
89 into high-latitude communities (Kumagai et al., 2018; Smale et al., 2019; Vergés et al., 2019;
90 Visser, 2008) and local rearrangements of species abundance (Tuckett, de Bettignies, Fromont,
91 & Wernberg, 2017) can outweigh the direct influence of species range shifts on the changes in
92 contemporary high-latitude community compositions. As such, understanding of the direct
93 effects of progressive warming (e.g. gradual influx of tropical species), as well as the indirect
94 effects of climate-mediated changes in species interactions and niche availability (e.g. the
95 persistence and proliferation of resident high-latitude species) is fundamental to predicting
96 changes in high-latitude communities.

97

98 While the tropicalisation of high-latitude communities is primarily driven by the direct and

99 indirect effects of progressive warming, acute thermal anomalies impose punctuated stress
100 events that further alter the dynamics of resident high-latitude species (Smale et al., 2019). A
101 common trend observed among high-latitude marine communities under progressive warming
102 is a regime shift in foundation species from cold-adapted macroalgae to scleractinian corals
103 (Kumagai et al., 2018; Smale et al., 2019; Vergés et al., 2014; 2019). Notwithstanding their
104 increasing abundances, scleractinian corals at high-latitudes are also vulnerable to acute heat
105 stress. Similar to tropical corals, high-latitude corals suffer coral bleaching under thermal
106 conditions that exceed long-term local averages (Celliers & Schleyer, 2002; Cook, Logan,
107 Ward, Luckhurst, & Berg, 1990; Dalton & Carroll, 2011). The impacts of bleaching in the
108 tropics have been well-documented over the past three decades, and recent increases in the
109 frequency of mass bleaching events have caused large-scale mortality among corals on tropical
110 reefs (Hughes et al., 2017). While high-latitude coral assemblages along the coasts of Australia,
111 the Atlantic, Japan, and South Africa have also experienced varying degrees of bleaching in
112 previous years, the overall frequency of mass bleaching events has been considerably lower
113 than in the tropics (Abdo, Bellchambers, & Evans, 2012; Celliers & Schleyer, 2002; Cook et
114 al., 1990; Dalton & Carroll, 2011; Harrison, Dalton, & Carroll, 2011; Hongo & Yamano, 2013;
115 Loya et al., 2001; Schleyer, Kruger, & Celliers, 2008).

116

117 Similar to tropical reefs (Hughes et al., 2018b), bleaching at high-latitudes is characterised by
118 taxonomic differences in bleaching susceptibility and mortality, which can lead to changes in
119 assemblage structure (Dalton & Carroll, 2011; Floros et al., 2004; Hongo & Yamano, 2013;
120 Loya et al., 2001). Unfortunately, high-latitude regions are predicted to experience greater heat
121 stress than the tropics over the coming decades (Hobday & Pecl, 2013; Wu et al., 2012), which
122 is likely to result in increasingly frequent and intense regional bleaching events (Heron,
123 Maynard, van Hooidek, & Eakin, 2016; van Hooidek, Maynard, & Planes, 2013; van

124 Hooidonk et al., 2016). However, unlike their tropical counterparts, poleward range shifts
125 and/or expansions are unlikely for many high-latitude coral species because suitable habitats
126 are progressively unavailable toward the poles, such as in the high-latitude east coast of
127 Australia and South Africa (Harriott & Banks, 2002; Schleyer et al. 2018; but see Booth &
128 Sears, 2018; Greenstein & Pandolfi, 2008; Richards et al., 2016). Similar to other flora and
129 fauna (Jablonski, 2008; Parmesan, 2006), many high-latitude corals may therefore contract
130 their geographic ranges and be more prone to extinction as their habitats become unsuitable
131 under climate change and/or they are unable to compete with incoming vagrant species.
132 Understanding the effects of punctuated stress events (e.g. thermal anomalies leading to
133 bleaching) on high-latitude coral assemblages provides critical insights into the emerging
134 changes in high-latitude community configurations over the coming decades.

135

136 In this study, we focus on the scleractinian coral assemblages of high-latitude coastal eastern
137 Australia that harbour diverse yet spatially patchy coral assemblages (Dalton & Roff, 2013;
138 Harriott & Banks, 2002; Sommer et al., 2017). These assemblages are inhabited by a subset of
139 species from the nearby, tropical Great Barrier Reef (GBR) to the north, and by subtropical
140 specialists that are either rare in the tropics or endemic to the region (Baird, Hoogenboom, &
141 Huang, 2017; Schmidt-Roach, Miller, & Andreakis, 2013; Veron, 2000). These coral
142 assemblages are increasingly susceptible to environmental stress as bleaching and disease
143 outbreaks are becoming more common under climate change (Dalton & Carroll, 2011; Dalton,
144 Godwin, Smith, & Pereg, 2010). During one of the harshest heat stress events recorded in the
145 region, the northern and central GBR suffered severe bleaching in 2016 (Hughes et al., 2017).
146 Here, we assess the impact of this heat stress event on the high-latitude coral assemblages
147 across 22 locations extending south of the GBR. Specifically, we investigate the relative
148 contributions of cumulative heat stress and local environmental history to the severity of

149 assemblage-scale and taxon-specific bleaching responses. Further, we quantify the importance
150 of taxonomic composition to assemblage-scale bleaching severity measurements. Lastly, we
151 discuss how taxonomic variability in bleaching vulnerability and immediate mortality, coupled
152 with geographic patterns in species composition, may lead to a reorganisation of high-latitude
153 coral assemblages. Together, the findings from this study improve our knowledge of the
154 vulnerability of high-latitude corals under climate change.

155

156 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

157 **Bleaching surveys and response metrics**

158 We surveyed a total of 8,952 coral colonies across 22 sites along the subtropical east coast of
159 Australia spanning 26°S to 31°S (Fig. 1) between April and May 2016, using rapid underwater
160 assessment methods described below. The timing of our April survey coincided with the peak
161 of heat stress at 19 of the survey sites. Three additional sites (Black Rock, Cook Island, and
162 Julian Rocks) were surveyed in May, within six weeks of maximum heat stress. At each site, a
163 1 m² quadrat was placed every 5 m along three or four 25 m belt transects, laid at a depth
164 between 3 and 13 m depending on the topography and depth profile of each location. In each
165 quadrat, all coral colonies were identified to the genus level. Recent changes to the
166 nomenclature of regional species (Table S1) included divisions and synonymy of a few genera
167 (Arrigoni et al., 2016; Budd, Fukami, Smith, & Knowlton, 2012; Huang, Benzoni, Arrigoni, et
168 al., 2014a; Huang, Benzoni, Fukami, et al., 2014b). Members of the synonymised genera
169 showed minimal bleaching severity and no immediate mortality, suggesting negligible impact
170 of taxonomic updates on bleaching patterns found among the synonymised genera (Table S2).
171 The health of each colony was visibly assessed *in situ* and scored as a categorical variable with
172 five levels: (0) no visible bleaching, (1) 1-20% of the colony bleached, (2) 21-50% bleached,
173 (3) 51-80% bleached, and (4) 81-100% bleached. Pigmentation patterns of a coral can differ

174 depending on environmental conditions and location (Brown, Dunne, Ambarsari, Le Tissier,
 175 & Satapoomin, 1999; Fitt, McFarland, Warner, & Chilcoat, 2000; Wallace, Fellegara, Muir, &
 176 Harrison, 2009). Therefore, signs of pigmentation, such as a mottled or pale appearance, were
 177 not included in the bleaching severity measurements, providing a conservative estimate of
 178 bleaching responses. Coral colonies were scored as ‘recently dead’ (i.e. immediate post-
 179 bleaching mortality) when live tissue was lost completely from the skeleton and an initial
 180 colonisation of turf algae was evident.

181

182 The severity of the bleaching response for each coral genus was calculated for each survey
 183 replicate as the weighted mean of the five health assessment categories (0-4, detailed above),
 184 adjusted by the proportion of coral colonies in each category (i.e. bleaching index – measure
 185 of taxon-specific bleaching response; modified from McClanahan, Baird, Marshall, &
 186 Toscano, 2004; Eq. 1);

$$187 \quad \text{Bleaching index (BI)} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{i * x_i}{X} \right), \text{ where } X = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

188 where n is the number of health assessment categories ($n = 5$ in this study), with an increase in
 189 the category value (i) indicating an increase in bleaching severity, and x_i is the number of coral
 190 colonies in the i^{th} category. A bleaching index value of 0 indicates none of the colonies are
 191 affected by bleaching, and a value of 1 indicates that all colonies within a genus were affected
 192 under the highest severity category. To obtain an estimate of site-level bleaching severity, we
 193 used the site susceptibility index (SSI – measure of assemblage-scale bleaching response) that
 194 considers the regional BI of each genus and weights the relative abundance of each genus
 195 present at a specific site (modified from McClanahan et al., 2007b; Eq. 2);

$$196 \quad \text{Site susceptibility index (SSI)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\mu_{BI_i} * x_i) * 100}{X}, \text{ where } X = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \text{ (Eq. 2)}$$

197 where n is the number of taxa (i.e. genera) present at a site, μ_{BI_i} is the mean bleaching index for
198 the i^{th} taxon across the region, and x_i is the number of coral colonies for the i^{th} genus at the site.
199 Unlike the bleaching index, the site susceptibility index does not have a maximum positive
200 value limit. Higher SSI values indicate higher assemblage-scale susceptibility, and 0 SSI
201 suggests no colonies at the site were affected, irrespective of the taxonomic composition of the
202 assemblage.

203

204 **Environmental data**

205 To examine the effects of local-scale variability in cumulative heat stress and of long-term
206 environmental parameters on assemblage-scale and taxon-specific bleaching responses, we
207 compiled a suite of remote sensing satellite data. The Degree Heating Week (DHW) metric
208 was used as a measure of heat stress and calculated using version 3.1 of the NOAA Coral Reef
209 Watch dataset at 5 km spatial resolution (Liu et al., 2014). The conventional DHW metric
210 accumulates SST anomalies exceeding 1°C above the long-term maximum of the monthly
211 mean (MMM) climatology (hereafter DHW_{1C}). To assess the potential effect of low-magnitude
212 heat stress, we also computed DHW with the same MMM climatology, but without the 1°C
213 filter (hereafter DHW_{0C}; van Hooidonk & Huber, 2009). For any given heat stress event,
214 DHW_{0C} is greater than DHW_{1C} as it includes contributions when SST exceeds the MMM by
215 less than 1°C. We compared temperature measurements between remote sensing satellite and
216 *in situ* logger data (present at seven sites) to assess the robustness of our heat stress
217 measurements and long-term environmental parameters obtained from satellite data. Our
218 analysis showed that the satellite data provided robust approximations of *in situ* thermal
219 conditions (site-specific Pearson's correlation coefficients between satellite and logger were
220 between 0.88 and 0.92, with all p-values < 0.001; Fig. S1; Table S3).

221

222 Long-term environmental parameters derived from remote sensing satellite data included long-
223 term means of the hottest month of each year, and annual variability in thermal conditions and
224 solar irradiance. These parameters were selected based on experimental and *in situ* evidence in
225 the literature that showed their direct influence on bleaching severity (Brown, Dunne, Goodson,
226 & Douglas, 2002; Hoegh-Guldberg, 1999; Lesser, Stochaj, Tapley, & Shick, 1990;
227 McClanahan, Maina, Moothien-Pillay, & Baker, 2005). Long-term mean water temperature of
228 the hottest month of each year between 1985 and 2015 (hereafter SST_{LTMAX}) was used as a
229 measure of the upper-bound thermal conditions at each site. Using the same sea surface
230 temperature (SST) data, variability in thermal conditions (hereafter SST_{VAR}) was calculated as
231 the long-term mean of the standard deviation of annual SST. Further, we calculated annual
232 variation in solar irradiance (hereafter PARZ_{VAR}) as the long-term mean of the standard
233 deviation of annual photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) between 2002 and 2015. The
234 amount of PAR reaching the benthos decreases with depth and with increasing turbidity (Read,
235 Rose, Winslow, & Read, 2015), and we adjusted the PAR values at each site accordingly (i.e.
236 PARZ; Pierson, Kratzer, Strömbeck, & Håkansson, 2008; Eq. 3);

237
$$PARZ = PAR_0 * e^{(-K490 * Z)} \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

238 where PAR_0 is PAR on the surface, $K490$ is the diffuse attenuation coefficient (a measure of
239 turbidity), and Z is the survey depth at each site. SST_{VAR} and PARZ_{VAR} are particularly relevant
240 for high-latitude reefs because the monthly and seasonal fluctuations of these parameters are
241 greater in high-latitude regions than most locations in the tropics (Beger, Sommer, Harrison,
242 Smith, & Pandolfi, 2014; Malcolm, Davies, Jordan, & Smith, 2011; Sommer, Beger, Harrison,
243 Babcock, & Pandolfi, 2018). SST_{LTMAX} and SST_{VAR} were calculated using version 3.1 of the
244 NOAA Coral Reef Watch dataset at 5 km spatial resolution (Liu et al., 2014). PAR and K490
245 data were obtained from the Global Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS)
246 Aqua Satellite products at 4 km resolution (Parkinson, 2003).

247

248 **Data analyses**

249 **Assemblage-scale bleaching response**

250 Before examining the effects of environmental parameters and taxonomic composition on
251 assemblage-scale bleaching responses, we first checked for multicollinearity of environmental
252 parameters using Pearson's correlation coefficient and variance inflation factor (VIF) with cut-
253 offs of $r = \pm 0.65$ and $VIF = 2$, respectively (Craney & Surles, 2007; Gordon, 2015). DHW_{1C}
254 showed a higher VIF value and larger Pearson's correlation coefficients with other
255 environmental variables than those exhibited by DHW_{0C} . Therefore, DHW_{0C} was used in all
256 our models (Fig. S2; Table S4). Subsequently, we evaluated a variety of variable combinations
257 using the widely applicable information criterion (WAIC) and leave-one-out cross-validation
258 (LOO) to select the final model (Table S5; Vehtari, Gelman, & Gabry, 2017). The final model
259 included DHW_{0C} , SST_{LTMAX} , SST_{VAR} , and $PARZ_{VAR}$ as independent environmental parameters.
260 VIF and model selection criteria were computed using the 'usdm' (Naimi, Hamm, Groen,
261 Skidmore, & Toxopeus, 2014) and 'loo' (Vehtari et al., 2017) packages. All modelling and
262 analyses in this study were conducted in R (R Core Team 2018).

263

264 We used hierarchical Bayesian generalised linear models with student's t-distribution to assess
265 the effects of heat stress, long-term environmental parameters, and the relative abundance of
266 each taxon in an assemblage on regional assemblage-scale (SSI) bleaching responses. To
267 account for spatial autocorrelation stemming from geographic clustering of survey sites, survey
268 site location was included as a random effect after categorisation into seven groups based on
269 geographic proximity and shelf position: Inner Moreton Bay, Outer Moreton Bay, Northern
270 New South Wales, Inshore Solitary Islands, Mid-shelf Solitary Islands, Offshore Solitary
271 Islands, and Central New South Wales (see Table S6 for detailed site information). Models

272 were executed in Stan (Carpenter et al., 2017) with weakly informative normal priors assigned
273 for beta parameters and gamma priors for degrees of freedom. All Stan models were called
274 from R using the ‘rstan’ package (Stan Development Team 2018). Each model was run with
275 four chains of 20,000 iterations; the first 10,000 iterations were discarded as warm-up, and all
276 subsequent iterations were sampled. We examined all chains for model convergence, the
277 adequacy of warm-up, and autocorrelation (Fig. S3). The Gelman-Rubin diagnostic (\hat{R})
278 compares the variance of each chain to the compiled variance of all chains, and values under
279 1.001 are desirable to ensure appropriate chain convergence (Gelman & Shirley, 2011). \hat{R}
280 values for all parameters of the assemblage-scale response models were equal to or below 1.
281 Model fits were summarised using the highest posterior density (HPD) interval as the credible
282 interval, and median point estimates for all chains were computed.

283

284 **Taxon-specific bleaching responses**

285 Taxonomic variability in overall bleaching severity across our survey sites was tested by
286 comparing the bleaching index (BI) of the five most abundant genera (*Acropora*, *Goniastrea*,
287 *Pocillopora*, *Porites*, and *Turbinaria*) using an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey’s
288 post-hoc test. We also used generalised additive models (GAM) to test whether the taxon-
289 specific BI was linked to the relative proportion of ‘recently dead’ colonies (i.e. immediate
290 mortality). *Goniastrea* and *Turbinaria* were excluded from the mortality analysis as they
291 suffered no or negligible mortality (*Goniastrea*: no mortality; *Turbinaria*: one colony mortality
292 across all survey sites). GAMs were run using the ‘mgcv’ package in ‘R’ (Wood, 2011).

293

294 The influence of heat stress and long-term environmental parameters on the taxon-specific
295 bleaching index (BI) was examined using a hierarchical Bayesian beta regression model with
296 logit link. The taxon-specific response model was restricted to the same five most abundant

307 genera and executed in Stan (Carpenter et al., 2017), with weakly informative normal priors
308 assigned for beta parameters and gamma priors for the dispersion parameter. In addition to the
309 geographic group random effect in the assemblage-scale models (Table S6), survey site
300 locations were included as a second random effect nested in geographic group to account for
301 survey replicates within the same site. The taxon-specific BI values were transformed using a
302 data range compression method (Smithson & Verkuilen, 2006) to preserve crucial information
303 in zero (no bleaching) values. The taxon-specific response model was run with the same
304 number of chains, iterations, and warm-up as the assemblage-scale response models (model
305 diagnostics – Fig. S4). \hat{R} values for all parameters of the taxon-specific response model were
306 equal to or below 1.

307

308 **Inferring Bayesian results**

309 Estimated model coefficients (β coefficients) indicate the modelled effect of a given predictor
310 on bleaching severity. Positive and negative β coefficients suggest corresponding strength of
311 positive or negative correlation between a given predictor variable (environmental parameter,
312 relative abundance of taxa) and the response variable (bleaching severity). The HPD intervals
313 reflect the distribution of β coefficients (i.e. distribution of modelled effects of a predictor on
314 bleaching severity) that is supported by the data. A high precision of β coefficients leads to a
315 high probability density and narrow posterior distribution of β coefficients, whereas low
316 precision of β coefficients results in low probability density and wide posterior distribution of
317 β coefficients.

318

319 **Spatial patterns of coral bleaching impacts**

320 To examine spatial patterns of taxon-specific bleaching severity and their subsequent impacts
321 on local assemblage structures, we examined the correlation between taxon-specific bleaching

322 severity of the five most abundant genera and latitude, as well as the correlation between their
323 relative abundances and latitude using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The Coffs Harbour
324 region has the most extensive high-latitude coral assemblages along the east coast of Australia,
325 whereas assemblages elsewhere in the region are generally more patchy in their distribution
326 with considerably lower coral cover (Fig. 1; Dalton & Roff, 2013; Harriott, Smith, & Harrison,
327 1994; Harriott & Banks, 2002). To examine whether the disproportionate concentration of
328 survey sites near Coffs Harbour skewed spatial patterns of bleaching severity and assemblage
329 compositions, we conducted a sensitivity test. A random number of survey replicates were
330 selected from the survey sites near Coffs Harbour and were combined with survey replicates
331 from other sites. Subsequently, these combined site datasets were used to test correlations
332 between taxon-specific bleaching index (BI) of the five most abundant genera and latitude, as
333 well as their relative abundances and latitude. This process was repeated 1,000 times and
334 summary statistics of the iterations were used to infer statistical significance of the correlations
335 between taxon-specific bleaching severity and latitude, and between relative abundance and
336 latitude.

337

338 **RESULTS**

339 **Assemblage-scale bleaching response**

340 The environmental parameters explored here did not capture the observed differences in
341 assemblage-scale bleaching severity (Site susceptibility index – SSI; Fig. 2a; Table S7). In
342 particular, estimated model coefficients for all environmental parameters were centred near
343 zero with wide posterior density intervals, indicating that these parameters were poorly
344 associated with the patterns of assemblage-scale bleaching responses. Model residuals also
345 showed no gradient pattern between all bivariate environmental variable combinations,
346 indicating that two-way interactive effects between tested environmental variables also were

347 unrelated to assemblage-scale bleaching severity (Fig. S5). In contrast, the variation in
348 taxonomic composition among assemblages was linked to the site susceptibility index (SSI).
349 The relative abundance of *Pocillopora*, in particular, was strongly associated with SSI (Fig. 2b;
350 Table S8). SSI was higher at sites where *Pocillopora* was more abundant. Posterior density
351 intervals of β coefficients for other genera, including regionally common *Acropora*, *Goniastrea*,
352 *Porites*, and *Turbinaria*, were wide and crossed zero, indicating an unlikely association
353 between the relative abundance of these genera and assemblage-scale bleaching severity.

354

355 **Taxon-specific bleaching responses**

356 Taxon-specific bleaching severity and immediate mortality were strikingly different among the
357 five most abundant genera (Fig. 3; Table S9; Table S10). Among the five most abundant genera,
358 *Pocillopora* and *Porites* were significantly more susceptible to bleaching than *Acropora*,
359 *Goniastrea*, and *Turbinaria* (Fig. 3a; Table S9). Despite the similarity in the bleaching index
360 (BI) values of the two severely impacted genera, they differed in patterns of mortality; mortality
361 rose as BI increased for *Pocillopora*, whereas mortality and BI were not correlated for *Porites*
362 (Fig. 3d; Fig. 3e; Table S10). *Acropora*, *Goniastrea*, and *Turbinaria* also had similar degrees
363 of bleaching to one another, and exhibited little or no bleaching (Fig. 3a; Table S9) or mortality
364 (Fig. 3b; Fig. 3c; Fig. 3f; Table S10).

365

366 The taxon-specific bleaching severity (BI) was associated with environmental predictors, yet
367 the specific predictors that affected bleaching severity responses differed among genera (Fig.
368 4; Table S11). Bleaching worsened with increasing heat stress (DHW) for *Porites* (Fig. 4a),
369 whereas *Pocillopora* bleached more at sites where water temperature was historically cooler
370 (SST_{LTMAX} ; Fig. 4b), or experienced higher fluctuations in annual solar irradiance ($PARZ_{VAR}$;
371 Fig. 4d). The bleaching severities of *Pocillopora* and *Porites* were not linked to the annual

372 variation in historical water temperature (SST_{VAR} ; Fig. 4c). Contrary to the clear associations
373 between bleaching severity and environmental parameters found among *Pocillopora* and
374 *Porites*, bleaching severities of *Acropora*, *Goniastrea*, and *Turbinaria* were not correlated with
375 any of the examined environmental parameters. Overall absolute model residuals were low for
376 *Acropora*, *Goniastrea*, and *Turbinaria*, whereas *Pocillopora* and *Porites* showed considerably
377 higher absolute model residuals without a notable pattern between all bivariate environmental
378 variable combinations (Figure S6).

379

380 **Spatial patterns of bleaching severity**

381 The geographic pattern in bleaching severity (BI) and the relative effect of bleaching on local
382 populations differed among genera (Fig. 5; Fig. S7; Fig. S8; Table S12). Overall, the severity
383 of bleaching response for the genus *Acropora* was minimal and did not vary across latitude
384 (Table S12; mean $r = -0.26$, $R^2 = 0.07$, $p = 0.12$), while the relative proportion of *Acropora* in
385 assemblages declined toward higher latitudes (Fig. 5a; mean $r = -0.55$, $R^2 = 0.3$, $p < 0.01$).
386 Bleaching severity of *Goniastrea* declined toward higher latitudes (Fig. 5b; mean $r = -0.54$, R^2
387 $= 0.29$, $p < 0.01$), without a corresponding change in relative abundance (Fig. 5a). Bleaching
388 was also less severe for *Turbinaria* toward higher latitudes (Fig. 5d; mean $r = -0.46$, $R^2 = 0.21$,
389 $p < 0.01$), yet its relative contribution to the total species assemblage increased with latitude
390 (Fig. 5a; mean $r = 0.56$, $R^2 = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$). In contrast, bleaching severity for *Pocillopora*
391 increased with latitude (Fig. 5c; mean $r = 0.51$, $R^2 = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$), without a significant
392 change in its relative abundance across latitude (Fig. 5a; mean $r = 0.23$, $R^2 = 0.06$, $p = 0.12$).
393 There was no correlation between bleaching severity (Table S12; mean $r = 0.002$, $R^2 = 0.004$,
394 $p = 0.85$) or relative abundance and latitude for *Porites* (Fig. 5a; mean $r = 0.32$, $R^2 = 0.12$, $p =$
395 0.08).

396

397 **DISCUSSION**

398 Analysis of the spatial and taxonomic patterns of coral bleaching allows us to identify specific
399 coral taxa or assemblages vulnerable to climate change and to predict future configurations of
400 coral assemblages (Hughes et al., 2018a; 2018b; Loya et al., 2001; van Woesik, Sakai, Ganase,
401 & Loya, 2011). Our findings highlight that in high-latitude eastern Australia, assemblage-scale
402 patterns of coral bleaching are heavily influenced by local abundance of a regionally common
403 genus sensitive to heat stress, *Pocillopora*, instead of environmental gradients. Further, the
404 clear distinction in taxon-specific bleaching severity and immediate mortality, coupled with
405 spatial patterns of taxon-specific bleaching responses and abundances, may lead to
406 simplification of assemblage structures and gradual homogenisation of reef functions.

407

408 **The importance of taxonomic composition in assemblage-scale bleaching responses**

409 Bleaching among the high-latitude coral assemblages along eastern Australia was initiated by
410 record heat stress in early 2016 (Fig. S9). Nevertheless, regional variability in the severity of
411 assemblage-scale bleaching responses (SSI – site susceptibility index) was poorly explained
412 by cumulative heat stress (Degree Heating Weeks) and long-term environmental conditions.
413 While remote sensing satellite data provided robust estimates of the regional variation in water
414 temperature (Fig. S1; Table S3), they were unlikely to capture fine temporal- and spatial-scale
415 variation in environmental conditions due to their coarser measurement scales than *in situ*
416 loggers (e.g. Castillo & Lima, 2010). It is plausible that these fine temporal- and spatial-scale
417 environmental parameters might include predictors that are better able to explain the observed
418 patterns of assemblage-scale bleaching severity, such as local high-frequency temperature
419 variability (Safaie et al., 2018).

420

421 Interestingly, the severity of assemblage-scale bleaching responses was associated with the
422 relative abundance of *Pocillopora*, a genus that is highly susceptible to heat stress (Fig. 3; Loya
423 et al., 2001; Marshall & Baird, 2000; McClanahan et al., 2004; van Woesik et al., 2011). By
424 definition, assemblage-scale bleaching metrics (e.g. SSI, Eq. 2) are influenced by both species
425 abundances and their respective bleaching responses. Severe bleaching of a single, locally
426 dominant species in an assemblage can produce a comparable SSI value (or an assemblage-
427 scale percentage of bleached corals) to another assemblage where many different species
428 experienced mild bleaching. As such, assemblage-scale metrics can be difficult to interpret or
429 may poorly explain the bleaching dynamics for coral assemblages characterised by high
430 variation in community structure. The close linkage between the abundance of bleaching-
431 susceptible taxa and assemblage-scale bleaching severity thus highlights the limitations of
432 assemblage-scale bleaching metrics and supports the idea that assessments of bleaching impact
433 should consider spatial variation in community composition and taxon-specific (e.g. species-
434 or genus-specific) bleaching responses (Marshall & Baird, 2000; Fitt, Brown, Warner, &
435 Dunne, 2001; Safaie et al., 2018).

436

437 **Taxon-specific environmental drivers of bleaching severity responses**

438 Contrary to the overall lack of association between environmental parameters and assemblage-
439 scale bleaching severity (SSI), taxon-specific bleaching (BI) patterns for *Porites* and
440 *Pocillopora* showed clear linkages to environmental parameters. Interestingly, *Porites* was the
441 only genus whose bleaching severity escalated with heat stress (Fig. 4a). *Porites* species with
442 massive growth forms are generally considered to be less sensitive to bleaching (Loya et al.,
443 2001; Marshall & Baird, 2000; McClanahan et al., 2004), yet encrusting *Porites* species, such
444 as those abundant along the high-latitude eastern Australia and at other high-latitude regions,
445 can be vulnerable to heat stress and susceptible to bleaching (Dalton & Carroll, 2011; van

446 Woesik et al., 2011). On the other hand, patterns of bleaching severity for *Pocillopora* were
447 best explained by long-term environmental conditions. Specifically, prior exposure to warm
448 temperature (SST_{LTMAX}) and low variability in solar irradiance ($PARZ_{VAR}$) reduced the severity
449 of bleaching. These patterns are consistent with previous findings, in which long-term exposure
450 to higher temperature was linked to a reduction in acute responses to heat stress (Brown et al.,
451 2002; Brown & Dunne, 2016; Griffin, Bhagooli, & Weil, 2006; Woolsey, Keith, Byrne,
452 Schmidt-Roach, & Baird, 2015). A recent study on *Pocillopora* also highlighted that
453 experimental transplantation of coral colonies from low to high fluctuations in PAR increased
454 the sensitivity of corals to heat stress (Sampayo et al., 2016). While previous studies indicated
455 that exposure to fluctuating water temperature might enhance thermal tolerance (McClanahan,
456 Ateweberhan, Muhando, Maina, & Mohammed, 2007a; Woolsey et al., 2015), we found that
457 fluctuation in annual water temperature had little effect on taxon-specific bleaching severity.
458 This lack of correlation between fluctuation in water temperature and taxon-specific bleaching
459 severity may be due to the narrower range of SST_{VAR} across our survey sites ($< 2.4^{\circ}C$)
460 compared to the previously reported experimental threshold for biological responses among
461 regional corals ($+4^{\circ}C$; Woolsey et al., 2015).

462

463 Patterns of bleaching severity for *Acropora*, *Goniastrea*, and *Turbinaria* were not linked to any
464 of the explored environmental parameters. The genus *Acropora* contains numerous tropical
465 species that tend to suffer severe bleaching and mortality during mass bleaching events
466 (Goreau, McClanahan, Hayes, & Strong, 2000; Hughes et al., 2019; Marshall & Baird, 2000;
467 McClanahan et al., 2004). However, our findings showed that high-latitude *Acropora* species,
468 such as *A. glauca* and *A. solitaryensis*, were resistant to heat stress. Low sensitivity to bleaching
469 among high-latitude *Acropora* spp. has also been reported in other parts of the globe,
470 highlighting distinctive bleaching resilience among high-latitude members of this genus

471 (Celliers & Schleyer, 2002; van Woesik et al., 2011; but see Hongo & Yamano, 2013). Overall,
472 the variability in taxon-specific bleaching responses under the same environmental conditions
473 observed across our study sites supports the notion that mild to moderate bleaching episodes
474 can identify locally/regionally resistant (e.g. *Goniastrea*, *Turbinaria*, and high-latitude
475 *Acropora* spp.) and vulnerable (e.g. *Pocillopora* and regional encrusting *Porites* spp.) taxa
476 (Hughes et al., 2017, 2018b; Loya et al., 2001; Marshall & Baird, 2000; van Woesik et al.,
477 2011). However, the distinction between bleaching tolerant and susceptible taxa likely varies
478 in space and with environmental conditions, such as local environmental history and
479 microhabitats (Safaie et al., 2018), and biological factors, including species identity, traits
480 (Mizerek, Baird, & Madin, 2018), and the presence of locally adapted genotypes (Bay &
481 Palumbi, 2014; LaJeunesse, Reyes-Bonilla, & Warner, 2007). Long-term studies that examine
482 taxon-specific bleaching mechanisms over a broad spatial scale are therefore needed to
483 understand shifts in ecosystem dynamics under climate change.

484

485 **Regional implications of taxonomic variability in bleaching impact and abundance**

486 Against the backdrop of species migrations (Baird, Sommer, & Madin, 2012) and
487 tropicalisation of high-latitude marine ecosystems (Smale et al., 2019; Vergés et al., 2014;
488 2019; Wernberg et al., 2016), taxon-specific bleaching, mortality, and spatial abundance
489 patterns have the potential to broadly affect ecosystem structure and functioning (Hughes et
490 al., 2003; 2018b; Pandolfi, Connolly, Marshall, & Cohen, 2011; Stuart-Smith, Brown,
491 Ceccarelli, & Edgar, 2018). While both *Pocillopora* and *Porites* experienced severe bleaching,
492 bleaching severity was only linked to immediate mortality of *Pocillopora* (Fig. 3d). Post-
493 bleaching mortality data from the Solitary Islands showed that the immediate mortality pattern
494 of *Pocillopora* observed in this study worsened, and *Pocillopora* suffered significant declines
495 in abundance (Cant et al. 2018). In contrast, *Turbinaria* was the only genus that experienced

496 mild bleaching, was more abundant at higher latitudes, and did not suffer severe bleaching or
497 mortality (Fig. 3f; Cant et al. 2018). These patterns suggest that recurrent bleaching and
498 mortality events may lead to increased dominance of *Turbinaria* and declines of *Pocillopora*
499 on high-latitude reefs, especially if the capacity for population recovery is affected by the
500 severity of bleaching (Hughes et al., 2019).

501

502 On tropical coral reefs, changes in assemblage composition following disturbance are largely
503 a function of other tropical taxa filling gaps in physical space vacated by vulnerable taxa
504 (Stuart-Smith et al., 2018). On high-latitude reefs, loss of vulnerable taxa potentially creates
505 opportunities for thermally-resilient local/regional taxa and incoming tropical taxa that benefit
506 from warming temperatures at high latitudes, thereby introducing new sets of life-history traits
507 to the ecosystem (Beger et al., 2014; Greenstein & Pandolfi, 2008; Sommer et al., 2018). For
508 example, corals on tropical coral reefs exhibit diverse growth forms and create complex three-
509 dimensional frameworks, whereas corals on high-latitude reefs tend to have more uniform or
510 less diverse morphologies (Sommer, Harrison, Beger, & Pandolfi, 2014), generally resulting
511 in structurally less complex coral framework toward higher latitudes (DeVantier, De'Ath,
512 Turak, Done, & Fabricius, 2006; Mizerek, Baird, Beaumont, & Madin, 2016). Therefore, loss
513 of species in high-latitude assemblages and replacement by tropical taxa could not only lead to
514 a change in the assemblage composition, but also result in a significant shift in habitat
515 complexity. However, the growth of structurally complex tropical taxa at high-latitudes may
516 be inhibited by chemical conditions increasingly less conducive to calcification with climate
517 change (e.g. ocean acidification; van Hooidonk, Maynard, Manzello, & Planes, 2014) or by
518 oceanographic conditions particularly unfavourable for corals with complex morphologies
519 (e.g. strong wave actions; Harriott & Banks, 2002). Such conditions may hamper the poleward
520 range expansion of tropical corals, in which case, the marked disparity in taxon-specific

521 bleaching severity and mortality will likely lead to proliferation of resident bleaching-resistant
522 corals and a homogenisation of assemblages, which in turn can impair ecosystem functioning
523 (Clavel, Julliard, & Devictor, 2011; McKinney & Lockwood, 1999).

524

525 **Outlook and conclusion**

526 The resilience of coral reefs to environmental anomalies is rapidly weakening as corals are
527 exposed to extreme conditions more frequently, and their capacity to rebound is declining
528 (Heron et al., 2016; Hughes et al. 2019; van Hooidonk et al., 2013; van Woesik et al., 2011).

529 While high-latitude reefs have been considered as potential climate refugia for tropical corals
530 under climate change (Beger et al., 2014; Riegl, 2003; but see Lybolt et al., 2011), our findings
531 suggest that resident high-latitude corals are also vulnerable to thermal anomalies, potentially
532 without suitable *ex situ* climate refugia equivalent to those of tropical corals (Harriott & Banks,
533 2002; Schleyer et al., 2018). The levels of heat stress measured among subtropical assemblages
534 were relatively low (DHW_{0C} of 4-9°C-weeks) compared to those recorded in the tropics during
535 the same time period of 2016 (up to DHW_{1C} of 12°C-weeks; Hughes et al., 2017). Nonetheless,
536 bleaching was prevalent throughout the region and resulted in severe bleaching of two abundant
537 genera, *Pocillopora* and *Porites*. This is particularly concerning because some representatives
538 of these genera are endemic species (*Pocillopora aliciae* Schmidt-Roach et al., 2013) or rare
539 in the tropics (*Porites heronensis* Veron, 1985). Loss of endemic or locally abundant taxa is
540 more than a simple loss of biodiversity as it can undermine ecosystem processes (e.g. energy
541 flow), deprive the ecosystem of novel ecological interactions (Bailey, Wooley, Lindroth, &
542 Whitham, 2006; Gorman, Potts, Schweitzer, & Bailey, 2014; Valiente-Banuet et al., 2015), and
543 incur a critical loss in evolutionary history for the taxonomic group (Huang & Roy, 2013; 2015).
544 The degree of changes in the ecological functions of high-latitude coral assemblages, and the
545 ability of high-latitude areas to act as climate refugia for tropical taxa will depend upon

546 recovery patterns of bleaching-susceptible regional taxa, range expansion rates of tropical taxa,
547 the relative strength of competitive advantages that resident high-latitude corals possess over
548 the ability of tropical corals to colonise the rocky substrates in the subtropics, and the frequency
549 and magnitude of recurrent environmental anomalies. Importantly, our mechanistic
550 understanding of coral bleaching, and efforts to predict the future of reefs are nullified under
551 extreme and unprecedented thermal conditions (Hughes et al., 2017), making the reduction of
552 global warming an urgent priority.

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860

861 **Figure 1.** Survey locations along the subtropical east coast of Australia spanning 26°S to 31°S.

862 Black dots mark the location of each survey site and red polygons indicate the known presence
 863 of coral assemblages.

864

865

866 **Figure 2.** The effects of (a) environmental variables and (b) taxonomic composition on
 867 assemblage-scale bleaching severity. Points indicate the median of the 95% highest posterior
 868 density (HPD) intervals of β coefficients, and horizontal lines indicate the 95% HPD intervals.
 869 Statistical significance is inferred where the 95% HPD interval does not intersect 0 and is
 870 annotated with a closed symbol. A positive β coefficient represents a positive association and
 871 a negative β coefficient indicates a negative association between assemblage-scale bleaching

872 severity (SSI) and (a) an environmental variable or (b) relative abundance of a genus. The
 873 genera annotated with an asterisk have undergone a recent taxonomic revision (Table S1).

874

875

876 **Figure 3.** Intergeneric variability in (a) bleaching index (BI) and (b-f) the relationship between
 877 bleaching index (BI) and immediate mortality for *Acropora*, *Goniastrea**, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*,
 878 and *Turbinaria*. The genera in (a) are grouped based on statistical similarity in bleaching index
 879 (brackets A and B). The box plots illustrate interquartile ranges of BI for each genus, whiskers
 880 indicate minimum and maximum values not exceeding 1.5 times below and above the first and

881 third quartiles (i.e. Tukey's boxplot) and dots indicate outliers. (b-f) Each dot represents the
 882 mean BI and immediate mortality for the taxon at each of the survey sites. Horizontal and
 883 vertical lines represent 95% confidence intervals for the mean values. Splines were estimated
 884 using generalised additive models with only significant relationships shown, and the shaded
 885 areas represent 95% confidence intervals (Table S10). Note the figures (b-f) are on different y-
 886 axis scales.

887

888

889 **Figure 4.** The effect of environmental variables on taxon-specific bleaching severity for: (a)
 890 Degree Heating Weeks (DHW_{0C}), (b) long-term mean water temperature of hottest month of
 891 each year (SST_{LTMAX}), (c) long-term mean of annual fluctuations in water temperature
 892 (SST_{VAR}), and (d) long-term mean of annual fluctuation in solar irradiance ($PARZ_{VAR}$). Points
 893 indicate the median of the 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals of β coefficients, and
 894 lines indicate the 95% HPD intervals. Statistical significance is annotated with a closed symbol.
 895 A positive β coefficient represents a positive association and a negative β coefficient indicates
 896 a negative association between an environmental variable and taxon-specific bleaching severity
 897 (BI).

899

900 **Figure 5.** (a) The relative contribution of the five most abundant genera (*Acropora*,
 901 *Goniastrea**, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*, and *Turbinaria*) and all remaining genera (Others) to
 902 assemblage composition across latitude. Sites are grouped based on geographic proximity for
 903 graphical purposes. Direct correlation between relative abundance and latitude can be found in
 904 Table S12. (b)-(d) The bleaching index (BI) for three of the five most abundant genera across
 905 latitude. Each point represents the mean BI for a survey site. Vertical lines are 95% confidence

906 intervals for the mean BI values. The slope of regressions indicates the relationship between
907 latitude and BI. Only statistically significant relationships are depicted.